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Faculty of Information Technology and Bionics

MSC THESIS

3D environment sensing with the
HoloLens 2 device

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Computer Science Engineering MSc

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Thesis Proposal Form

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Title: 3D environment sensing with the HoloLens 2 device

Summary of the thesis:

Today's development trends are increasingly pointing towards wearable smart devices. Among these are the very popular smart-glasses, which can be used to create various interactive experiences based on augmented or virtual reality systems. To enhance the user experience, these devices offer a variety of advanced sensors that provide different types and qualities of information about the user's environment. The optimal data extraction, however, requires the development of specific methods due to the unique sensor design. The main objective of this thesis is to develop an algorithmic toolkit that uses the sensor measurements of the Microsoft HoloLens 2 as an intelligent data collection device to efficiently map, interpret and complete the user's three-dimensional environment.

Detailed task description:

- Introduce the Microsoft HoloLens 2 smart device, describe the sensors used for sensing and the data they generate.
- Investigate the quality and possible limitations of the point cloud from your smart device's depth camera, based on indoor and outdoor data.
- Introduce and explore different ways to complete the images taken by the smart device's depth-sensing camera. As a part of this, describe the basic concepts and mathematics of depth-image completion in case of different methods.
- Examine the results of the implemented methods in indoor and outdoor recordings.
- Analyze them in terms of effectiveness and robustness, specify future improvements.
- Investigate the use-cases of the described algorithm in real-world scenarios.

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Declaration of Authenticity

I, the undersigned József Kövendi, student of the Faculty of Information Technology and Bionics at the Pázmány Péter Catholic University, hereby declare that I have prepared the present thesis myself without any unauthorized help, and that I have only used the sources specified in the thesis. I have clearly marked all parts that I have literally taken from other sources or have rewritten or translated while keeping the meaning of the original text, also indicating the source thereof. I have not submitted this thesis to any other study programs.

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Abstract

In recent years the increasing popularity of smart devices such as smartphones, smartwatches and smart home devices can be attributed to rapid technological advancements and a growing demand for integrating digital capabilities into our daily lives. This trend is driven by the desire for more natural interactions with digital content and an enhanced user experience. One of the most promising and rapidly developing fields of smart devices is the field of wearable smart glasses, more precisely the field of augmented reality (AR) devices. The main purpose of these devices is to provide a hands-free experience for the user, while still being able to interact with digital content by introducing a digital layer into the physical environment. At the time of writing this thesis the leading product in the space of augmented reality devices and smart glasses is the HoloLens 2, developed by Microsoft. The HoloLens 2 is a mixed reality wearable smart device that allows users to interact with digital content with gestures and voice commands through a holographic interface. The device gained popularity and attention due to its potential applications in a variety of fields. The device is equipped with many different sensors, including a time-of-flight depth sensing camera, which is used for environment mapping. Due to its working principle, the sensor is strongly limited in terms of resolution, accuracy and range. The sensor has showed poor performance in case of strong sunlight and struggles to capture small and complex objects accurately.

The goal of this thesis work is to investigate possible solutions to overcome the limitations of the depth sensing camera by adapting different point cloud completion methods both in two- and three-dimensional space. Therefore, I will present the HoloLens 2 device in details and discuss the limitations of the device in different scenarios. I will also present two different methods for point cloud completion in two- and three-dimensional space. In doing so I will provide a technical background for both methods and I will present the results of the experiments that I conducted with the different methods focusing on indoor environments. As an outlook to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed methods I extended the scope of the research to outdoor environments as well.

Finally, I will summarize my findings and results of the experiments and I will discuss the limitations of the proposed methods and the possible future works and applications.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1. Motivation

In recent years, there has been an uptrend in the usage of smart devices that can be attributed to the rapid advancements in technology and the demand of integrating digital capabilities into our daily lives. From the most popular categories of smart devices the smart phones through smart watches and smart home devices, the popularity of these devices is unmistakably increasing. The main reason behind the rapid advancement of smart-device technology and numerous different wearable devices is a growing demand for a more natural way of interacting with digital content and more natural user experience.

One of the most promising and rapidly developing fields of smart devices is the field of wearable smart glasses, more precisely the field of augmented reality (AR) devices. The main purpose of these devices is to provide a hands-free experience for the user, while still being able to interact with the digital content. It introduces a digital layer into the physical environment, enabling interactions that were not possible before, opening up new possibilities in a variety of fields, such as manufacturing, healthcare, education, and more.

The HoloLens 2 is a flagship product in the space of augmented reality devices developed by Microsoft as a successor to the original HoloLens device. The HoloLens 2 is a mixed reality wearable smart device that allows users to interact with digital content in a natural way, using gestures and voice commands through a holographic interface. The device gained popularity and attention due to its potential applications in a variety of fields.

The main purpose of this thesis is to explore the capabilities of the HoloLens 2 device and to develop a proof of concept method that demonstrates the applicability of the

sensors of the device. The method is intended to complement the environment mapping capabilities of the device by providing a more accurate and detailed representation of the surroundings of the user.

1.2. Problem statement

In my experience, while using the device and throughout my previous works with the HoloLens 2 device I encountered some limitations regarding the capabilities of the device and more specifically the capabilities of the depth sensing camera. In some cases due to various reasons the depth sensing camera was not able to capture the environment in a sufficient quality to be used for further processing. The most common issues were encountered during capturing objects with relatively small size and big complexity. In this thesis, I aim to improve the quality of the captured environment focusing on smaller and complex objects in indoor environments. I have examined different approaches to overcome the limitations of the device by adapting different pointcloud completion methods both in two- and three-dimensional space.

As an outlook, to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed method I extended the scope of the research to outdoor environments as well.

1.3. Outline

The structure of the thesis follows the timeline of the research and the development of the proposed method. Firstly I will introduce and explore examples of environment completion methods and their principles in Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, I will introduce the HoloLens 2 device and its sensors and I will also discuss the limitations of the device that I encountered during my research in more details. I will then present the different methods in details and provide a technical background for each of them in Chapter 4. Then I will present the results of the experiments that I conducted with the different methods in Chapter 5. Finally, I will summarize the results of the experiments and I will discuss the limitations of the proposed method and the possible future works in Chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Related Works

2.1. Point cloud completion

The process of environment completion in terms of point cloud completion is a rapidly developing field of research. With the ever so decreasing cost of 3D sensors like depth sensing cameras and light detection and ranging sensors (LiDARs), which are laser based distance measuring sensors, point clouds became more and more accessible data format for the general public. Along with this wider accessibility and lower cost of the sensors the resulting scans became more and more noisy and incomplete, due to various reasons such as the low resolution of the sensors and occlusion of the scanned object. To overcome these limitations many different approaches were developed to complete the environment and point clouds in the three-dimensional space. The estimation of the missing parts of the point clouds is the cornerstone of the completion process and is a challenge in various fields of research in computer vision, robotics, for example in virtual or augmented reality applications [1].

The three-dimensional completion methods can be categorized into three main groups: geometry-based [2] for filling holes in point clouds, template-based [3] for completing point clouds by using a predefined template and finally deep learning-based methods like PointNet [4] or the Point Completion Network (PCN) [5]. The latter methods utilize deep learning to estimate the missing parts of the point clouds.

Point cloud completion can be performed using two- or three-dimensional methods. For a two-dimensional approach a good example is the ST-DepthNet [6] where range image sequences are used to complete the missing parts of a point cloud in real time which occurred due non-repetitive circular scanning of the Livox Avia LiDAR [7]. Using this device the resulting data is in 2.5D format, which means that the three-dimensional

space is captured through multiple partial scans of the environment.

A three-dimensional approach is used in the Point Completion Network (PCN) [5] where the missing parts of the point cloud are estimated using an encoder-decoder network. In case of PCN the number of points was limited to be used during completion, however in case of the Multi-View Based Point Cloud Completion Network (MVPCC-Net) [8] this limitation was overcome by relying on multiple views of the same object and completing the point cloud with enough points to represent the object's complexity in its entirety. This resulted in being able to complete extremely high resolution point clouds. In this case data that were used during training were generated from the ShapeNet [9] dataset. ShapeNet is a large scale dataset containing 3D CAD models of different objects in a variety of categories. The details of the ShapeNet dataset will be discussed in Chapter 4. By rendering the objects to images while keeping the points coordinates and color values and then an inpainting network was trained to complete the missing parts of the point clouds.

2.2. HoloLens 2 environment mapping

Mapping an environment is a complex task requiring multiple data types to complement each other. In case of the HoloLens 2 device the combined use of the depth sensing camera and the IMU can be used to create a spatial map of the environment. As shown in [10] and [11] the device was able to capture and reconstruct large scale environments with high accuracy. However, as highlighted in [11] in case of smaller objects the results were not as accurate and requires further investigation.

In case of reconstructing outdoor environments the range limitation is more prominent as it can be seen in the dataset recorded with the HoloLens 2 device in [12] where the small range of the depth sensing camera was significant.

Chapter 3

The Microsoft HoloLens 2 device

The HoloLens 2 is a mixed reality wearable smart device that allows users to interact with digital content in a natural way, using gestures and voice commands. The main purpose of the device is to provide a hands-free experience for the user, while still being able to interact with the digital content. The device is intended to be used in a variety of fields, such as manufacturing, healthcare, education, and more. The HoloLens 2 was released in 2019 and it is the second, improved generation of the HoloLens device [13]. The HoloLens 2 achieved the greatest improvement in user experience, computing power and the number and quality of sensors compared to its predecessor.

3.1. Design

The HoloLens 2 device [14] is designed to be worn on the head, with the front visor covering the user's eyes. The visor is transparent, thus enabling the user to see the real world while also being able to see the digital content that is being projected on the visor.

Wearing the device is comfortable even for longer periods of time due to its light weight (566 gram) and adjustable headband.

3.2. Hardware and Software

Hardware: The HoloLens 2 is equipped with a Qualcomm Snapdragon 850 SoC processor paired with 4 GB of RAM which enables synchronous usage of the different sensors and the display. The device has 64 GB of storage which is more than enough for the operating system and the applications that are installed on the device. Connectivity is provided by a Wi-Fi 5 and Bluetooth 5.0. The device is equipped with a USB-C port for charging and data transfer.

The device is powered by 27 watt battery which is enough for 2-3 hours of active usage. Charge time is approximately 1 hour and usage supported while charging.

Software: The HoloLens 2 runs on a modified version of Windows 10, called Windows Holographic, which is specifically designed to use with the HoloLens device. The device comes with many preinstalled applications. The device also supports the installation of custom applications that are developed for the HoloLens 2. The applications can be installed from the Microsoft Store or from the web browser.

3.3. Sensors

The HoloLens 2 is equipped with a variety of sensors which are capable of capturing different types of data. The location of the sensors are shown in Figure 3.1.

Eye tracking cameras: There are 2 infrared eye tracking cameras located on the inside of the visor. These cameras are used to track the user's eye movement.

Head tracking camera: There are 4 head tracking cameras located on the device which are capable of sensing the visible light spectrum. The cameras are used to track the user's head position and orientation. Two of these cameras are facing towards the

Figure 3.1: Location of the sensors on the HoloLens 2 device [14]

front in a stereo configuration (one on the left and one on the right), while the remaining 2 cameras are covering the peripheral areas on each side. These cameras are capable of capturing 480x640 resolution grayscale images at 30 frames per second.

RGB camera: On the front in the middle of the device there is a 8 megapixel RGB camera which is capable of capturing 1080p resolution images at 30 frames per second.

Depth sensing camera: The depth sensing camera is located in the front in the middle of the device right under the RGB camera. This sensor is capable of measuring the distances of the scene that is the field of view of the camera. The resulting image is a 288 x 320 grayscale image where each pixel contains a distance value in millimeters instead of a color value. The depth camera can be operated in two modes:

- **AHAT (Articulated Hand Tracking):** High frame rate (45 fps) near depth sensing that is used for hand tracking up to 1 meter.
- **Long Throw:** Low frame rate (1 - 5 fps) far-depth sensing for spatial mapping up to 5.5 meters.

IMU: Inertial measurement unit with accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer. The IMU is used to track the device's position and orientation in space.

3.3.1 Sensors' field of view

Due to the different locations of the sensors on the device, the field of view and the area that is covered by the sensors are different. The covered areas by each sensor are shown in Figure 3.2. As a result in case of sensor fusion the different sensors will capture different areas of the scene. The most notable example of this is when the RGB and the depth sensing camera are used together. The area covered by the depth sensing camera is bigger thus when the RGB image is used to color the depth image the resulting image will have a black border around it. This phenomenon can be seen on Figure 3.3 marked with red. This is an important remark as this effect is present throughout the thesis.

3.4. Limitations of data capturing

During my research with the HoloLens 2 device I encountered some limitations that has effected the results of my research. The main problem that effects all the sensors is that the time stamp of the captured data is not synchronized nor stable in terms of

Figure 3.2: Covered areas by the sensors on the HoloLens 2 device [15]

frames per second. This could be an issue in case of stereo calibration and sensor fusion. Furthermore, during capturing data streams with the device, in some cases the device has stopped recording or just recorded in an unusably low frame rate or the saved recording was corrupted thus could not be processed for later use.

3.5. Limitations of the depth sensing camera

Apart from the general limitations of the sensors, the depth sensing camera has some additional limitations that have to be taken into account when using the device. The depth sensing camera works on the principle of time of flight (TOF). This means that the camera emits an infrared light which bounces back from the object in the scene. The distance of the objects is measured through the time it takes for the light to return to the camera. The distance is calculated by dividing the time by the speed of light which is a known constant. Thanks to this principle the camera can be significantly smaller than other depth sensing devices, but this lightweight design comes with some compromises.

3.5.1 Range

As mentioned in the sensor specification the depth sensing camera has a limited range of 5.5 meters. As it can be seen on Figure 3.3 the depth image is black beyond a certain distance which is not that far away from the camera. This can be a problem in case

(a) Depth image

(b) Depth image with colors

(c) RGB image

Figure 3.3: Range limitation visualization

of capturing large scale environments limiting the use of the device to smaller areas like indoor environments.

3.5.2 Valid measurements

For depth cameras that are based on the time-of-flight principle it is important that the emitted infrared light only bounces once - ideally on the object which's distance is to be measured - before returning to the camera. This cannot be achieved in some cases. For example if the object is reflective or transparent the light can bounce multiple times before returning to the camera. Also in case of corners in a room the light can bounce multiple times due to the close proximity of the walls. These measurements are invalid and causes noise in the depth image.

Figure 3.4: Invalid measurements in case of a reflective object

Figure 3.5: Invalid measurements in case of a transparent object

Figure 3.6: Invalid measurements in case of a corner

On Figure 3.4 the error due to a reflective object - a laptop - can be seen. Most of the laptop is missing from the depth image resulting in black pixels. The effected area is marked with a red circle on the depth image.

On Figure 3.5 the error caused by a transparent object - a bottle - can be seen. Due to the transparency of the bottle the light can pass through it and bounce off the wall

behind it without being absorbed by the bottle. This results in the partial disappearance of the bottle from the depth image.

On Figure 3.6 the error caused by a corner can be seen. The close sharp edges of the corner causes the light to bounce multiple times resulting in invalid areas in the depth image.

3.5.3 Sunlight

The depth sensing camera is sensitive to sunlight. If the sunlight is strong enough it can interfere with the infrared light emitted by the camera. This can also cause invalid measurements and noise in the depth image. In most cases this happens when strong sunlight is bouncing off a surface the camera is facing towards or the strong sunlight directly shines into the sensor. On Figure 3.7 an example can be seen for the latter case. The depth image contains black pixels where the sunlight is shining into the sensor.

Figure 3.7: Invalid measurements in case of strong sunlight

Chapter 4

Methods

As I have mentioned in the Introduction 1, the goal of this thesis is to develop a method that enables the retrieval of the information and the data that is lost during data capturing with the depth sensing camera on the HoloLens 2 device. I have examined two different approaches to solve this problem. In my first approach I have tried a state-of-the-art deep learning based approach to solve the problem. In my second approach I have tried to solve the problem with a more direct and fact based method. The following sections will describe these two approaches in detail.

In both cases the main goal is to be able to complete the scene that is captured by the depth sensing camera. Since the depth sensing camera works reasonably well in case of larger objects, the main focus of thesis work is to be able to retrieve the information lost in case of smaller, complex shaped objects.

4.1. Method 1: Deep Learning based approach

In my first approach I have tried to complete the missing data with a deep learning based approach relying on the depth sensing camera alone. The main idea of this approach is to train a deep neural network with ground truth and bad image pairs enabling the neural network to learn the mapping between the bad image and the ground truth image. Once the network has seen enough training data that is varied enough to cover all the possible cases, the network should be able to complete the missing data on images it has not seen before. The main advantage of this approach is that it is very flexible and can be used to complete any kind of missing data if trained right, however it requires a lot of training data and it is very challenging to create a dataset that has enough data to cover all the possible cases.

At the time of writing I was not able to find an existing dataset that is suitable for this task which is to complete the missing specific areas of the depth image. For this I had to have ground truth images as well as the areas where I had to complete the missing data. To overcome this issue I have created my own dataset, which I will describe in detail in the following sections.

4.1.1 Dataset

The process to create an adequate dataset which contains the ground truth (GT) and the areas where the missing data should be completed (mask) can be broken down into several steps.

Data capturing

The first step at creating the dataset was to capture depth images of various objects, from various angles and distances. This was necessary because of two reasons. Firstly, to be able to train a robust network that is able to perform completion on any kind of depth image, the network has to be trained on images with a wide variety of orientations of different objects. The different orientations could be easily achieved by moving around an object during the data capture. By changing the HoloLens 2's position and orientation relative to the object different views of the object can be captured from different distances.

Secondly I had to have the captured objects in high definition to be able to create the GT images where the parts to be completed are not missing. This was not an easy problem to solve since I had to capture a high quality depth image with the same depth sensors that I was trying to improve. To overcome this issue I examined the problem from the perspective of when the faulty depth image capture happens.

Creating high resolution depth images of objects

The main problem happens when the object that is being captured is far from the depth camera and due to low resolution of the sensor it could happen that there are no infrared rays that bounce back from the object and thus the depth sensor cannot measure the distance of the object. By moving closer to the object while capturing the depth images this can be avoided. However, by doing this the object will not be captured in its entirety only parts of it will be captured. To have high quality depth images of the whole object I have utilized the IMU sensor of the HoloLens 2 device to track the device's position and orientation in space. The IMU captures the exact position of the HoloLens 2 device at

each timestamp, thus by combining the depth images captured at different positions and orientations I was able to create a high resolution depth image of the whole object. The HoloLens 2's API provides a method to combine the point clouds captured at different positions and orientations, however this method is mostly adequate for larger structures like rooms and buildings, because it uses an aggressive filtering method to remove the noise from the point clouds. This filtering method also removes the small objects from the point clouds, thus it is not suitable for my use case.

To achieve this first I had to represent the two-dimensional depth images in a three-dimensional space as point clouds. In case of the HoloLens 2 device this process can be easily accomplished. It is given for each pixel on the depth image where the light ray came from meaning the point the light ray bounced back from in the three-dimensional space. These directions of the light rays are given with a look-up table where for each pixel the direction of the light ray is given in the form of a three-dimensional vector with x, y and z coordinates. Since the depth image contains the distance of the object for each pixel, the three-dimensional coordinates of each pixel can be calculated by multiplying the direction vector with the distance value. This results in a point cloud where each point represents a pixel on the depth image.

Once all the depth images of an object are represented in the three-dimensional space as point clouds, the next step is to transform each point cloud to the same coordinate system. By default, the point clouds are in the camera coordinate system which does not contain any information about the position and orientation of the HoloLens 2 device, thus the point clouds cannot be combined. To be able to combine the partial point clouds that were captured from different positions and orientations, the point clouds have to be transformed to the world coordinate system, which is a coordinate system that is fixed to the real world. These transforms were captured along with the depth images using the IMU sensor. By applying the timestamp specific transform to the point clouds the whole object can be reconstructed in the world coordinate system.

Now that the whole object is reconstructed from many partial point clouds, the next step is to project the point clouds back to a two-dimensional image. This can be done using the pinhole camera model which is a widely used camera model in computer vision. The idea behind this model is to think of the camera as a pinhole, where the light rays that are coming from the object are concentrated at a single point - the pinhole - and the image is projected onto a plane that is behind the pinhole. These light rays that are being projected onto the plane are the points of the three-dimensional space and the

value of the points is the distance of the point that the light ray is coming from. This projection in practice can be performed by calculating the intersection of the light rays and the plane. This is achieved through implementing a virtual pinhole camera model by using the camera’s intrinsic parameters. The intrinsic parameters are the focal length of the camera and the coordinates of the principal point. The focal length is the distance between the pinhole and the plane where the image is projected and the principal point is the point where the optical axis intersects the image plane. The optical axis is the line that connects the pinhole and the principal point. A visual representation of the pinhole camera model can be seen on Figure 4.1.

The intrinsic parameters are specific to each camera. In case of the HoloLens 2 device the intrinsic parameters for the depth sensing camera are given and using them a matrix 4.1 can be formed that represents the virtual pinhole camera model. In this matrix f_x and f_y are the focal lengths of the camera and c_x and c_y are the coordinates of the principal point.

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

Once the virtual pinhole camera model is created the point clouds can be projected to the image plane. This can be done by multiplying the point cloud’s points with the virtual pinhole camera matrix resulting in the position of the points on the image plane. Since it is known which point from the point cloud is projected to which pixel on the image plane, the depth image can be created by calculating the distance of the points to the camera.

Point cloud filtering

Before projecting the combined point clouds to generate the GT images first they had to be filtered. The point clouds that are created from the depth images are not perfect, they contain a lot of noise and outliers. When combining the partial point clouds the noise and the outliers are also combined which results in a noisy point cloud. To keep only the relevant points of the point clouds I have applied a statistical outlier removal filter to the point clouds. This filtering method calculates the average distance of each point to its k nearest neighbours and if the distance of the point is greater than a threshold value it is removed from the point cloud. This method is very effective in removing the outliers and the noise from the point clouds, however it has its drawback. The threshold

value has to be set manually and it is not possible to set a threshold value that works for all the different objects.

GT image generation

To create the GT images I had to combine the high resolution depth images created from the merged point clouds with the original depth image captured by the HoloLens 2 device. This way I was able to create image pairs where I had the same view for both the GT and the original bad image. Achieving the same view for the GT and the original image was solved by using the IMU sensor's data to transform the merged point clouds to the same orientation from where the original depth image was captured. Once the merged point cloud was transformed to the same orientation the GT image could be created by projecting the merged point clouds to the same image plane from where the original depth image was captured using the virtual pinhole camera model.

Mask generation

To create the mask where I want the completion to happen I had to find the areas where the depth image is missing the objects. This can be done by comparing the original depth image with the GT image and saving the positions of the pixels where the depth image is missing the object but the GT image is not. This process can be presented with Equation 4.2 where p is the original depth image, m is the GT image and x and y are the coordinates of the pixels.

Figure 4.1: Pinhole camera model [16]

$$\begin{cases} 1 & ,if \quad p[x][y] = 0 \quad and \quad m[x][y] \neq 0 \\ 0 & ,if \quad p[x][y] = 0 \quad and \quad m[x][y] = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

4.1.2 Used network architecture

The neural network architecture that I utilized to solve the problem of depth image completion was a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [17] based neural network called EdgeConnect [18].

Generative Adversarial Network Architecture

GANs are a class of neural networks. The idea behind this network is to have two neural networks that are competing against each other. These networks are trained simultaneously and are called generator and discriminator. The process of training can be interpreted as a two-player minimax game, where the generator network tries to minimize the loss function while the discriminator network tries to maximize the loss function.

Generator: The generator network is a generative model that captures the distribution of the training data. The goal of the generator is to generate a sample that is indistinguishable from the training data.

Discriminator: The discriminator network is a discriminative model that is trained to distinguish between the generated samples and the training data. The comparison between the generated sample and the training data is done by the discriminator network and its goal is to maximize the probability of the generative network making a mistake.

EdgeConnect

EdgeConnect intends to improve image inpainting by utilizing the GAN architecture and by paying special attention to the edges of the inpainted area. Many other inpainting methods tend to blur the edges of the inpainted area which results a structureless image. To overcome this problem Edge Connect uses a two stage process both of which are based on the GAN architecture. In the first stage the network uses a generator G_1 and a discriminator D_1 to inpaint the missing edges of the masked area. For this the input is the input image's extracted edges. In this first stage the network aims to inpaint the edges of the masked area. The result of this first step is an edge map that contains the hypothetical edges of the masked area. This edge map is then fed into the second stage of

the network, which can be characterized with its own generator G_2 and discriminator D_2 . In this stage the network aims to inpaint the missing data of the masked area with color values based on the edge map that was generated in the first stage and the input image. Then in the second stage the network uses another generator G_2 and a discriminator D_2 to refine the image generated by the first stage by inpainting the missing data like a regular inpainting method would.

4.1.3 My implementation

To utilize the EdgeConnect architecture on depth images I have applied changes to the network to make it possible to use it with different data type and input quantity. For the network to be able to capture structures while completing I have fed three images, each with size 256×256 simultaneously to the network as one input. These images were of the same object but captured from different angles along with the corresponding masks. By doing this the network has more information about the object regarding the structure and three-dimensional shape. This was especially important in case of more complex objects, because in such cases images from a single view could miss important information about the object's three-dimensional shape.

During my research I have examined two different approaches. Both used the EdgeConnect as a base platform, and both needed some additional changes in the network.

Approach 1: Depth information based

In the first case I have simply relied on the depth image data which only contained the depth information of the scene from a given point in space. Two changes were applied to the network to accept depth images. First it was modified so that the expected number of color channels were 1 instead of 3 and secondly it was modified to accept a different data type than the original 8-bit unsigned integer format.

Input channel changes: Since the original network was created to work with RGB images the number of input channel was 3, one for each color channel (red, blue, green). In my case I had only one channel with the depth information. The input image shape is an important crucial parameter of any image based neural network, since the whole network structure is designed while keeping in mind the width, height and the number of channels of the input image. Applying the network on an image with different shape would result in an error.

Data type changes: EdgeConnect was expecting RGB images where each pixel is represented by three 8-bit unsigned integers. In 8 bits the representable unsigned integer values are between 0 and 255 ($2^8 - 1$). In case of depth images all the information has to be stored in a single channel. Considering this more bits had to be used for each pixel to be able to store the depth information with enough precision. Thus, the depth images were stored in a 16-bit unsigned integer format where the representable unsigned integer values are between 0 and 65535 ($2^{16} - 1$). This way more information was stored for each pixel, but the network was not able to process this data type. Fortunately a well-established technique called normalization is usually applied in case of neural networks. Normalization is the process of transforming the input data to a predefined range. This method was already in use in the original EdgeConnect implementation, thus changing the input range of the normalization process was enough to be able to use the network with depth images.

Approach 2: World coordinate based

To be able to capture further structural information about the objects I have also tried an approach where the input images were containing the depth values explicitly. This means that during the projection from the three-dimensional space to the two-dimensional image plane not the distance values between the point and the camera are stored but the three-dimensional coordinates of the point in the world coordinate system. This resulted in 3 channel images, where each channel contained the x, y and z coordinates of a point in 16-bit unsigned integers. Using these inputs the input channel's number became three thus this does not had to be changed in the network, but the data type related changes had to be applied again.

4.2. Method 2: Direct approach

In the second method I have tried to approach the problem from a more direct perspective. The main differences between this and the first method is that in this method I tried to solve the problem in the three-dimensional space while trying to limit relying on data that is captured by the depth sensing camera.

To achieve this I tried to limit the number of unknown variables by utilizing the RGB camera of the HoloLens 2 device as well as the depth sensing camera. By not relying solely on the depth image I was able to extract more features from the scene then before. Moreover, in this method the objects are not treated uniformly, instead the objects will

be classified and divided into two categories based on their shape. These categories were: bodies of revolution and every other object. The importance of this categorization will be explained in the following sections.

The main idea of this method is to remove the falsely captured objects and replace them with corresponding models of the objects. This way the missing data will be replaced with data that is known to be correct.

The steps of this algorithm can be broken down into 6 steps, where each step's successfulness depends on the previous steps.

4.2.1 Step 1: Object detection and segmentation

As I mentioned in the introduction one of the main idea of this method is to approach the problem in the three-dimensional space. To achieve this I first had to consider what options I had to be able to perform the object detection and segmentation in a way that the result will be in the three-dimensional space.

An obvious solution is to detect and segment the object in the three-dimensional space. This way I will not have any problem with transportation of the information from the two-dimensional space to the three-dimensional space. Although this is the most intuitive solution, it is not a viable one. In 3 dimensions the objects are represented as point clouds, which are unordered sets of points. This would introduce a lot of complexity to the problem. Moreover, the depth sensing camera is not able to capture the objects correctly - which is the problem I am trying to solve.

To overcome this I have looked into solutions that has already been used and well optimized. The most obvious solution was to use the RGB camera's images to perform the object detection and segmentation. With this the main problem was solved, but I have introduced a new one, which is to move the information from the RGB image to 3 dimensions. Since I have already worked out how can I project a two-dimensional depth image into 3 dimensions the 2D to 3D part was solved. Now I only have to transfer the segmentation information from the RGB image to the depth image meaning I have to find a way to create a correspondence between the pixels of the RGB image and the pixels of the depth image.

To produce the correspondence the transformations from the RGB camera's space to the depth camera's space has to be known. This transformation is not given explicitly, however it can be calculated. The most straightforward way to get this transform is to involve the world coordinate system which is a universal space for sensors and it represents

where a sensor is situated in the real world. For both of these cameras the transformation from the camera coordinate system to the world coordinate system is known, for each frame, thus by first moving the RGB image to the world coordinate system with the rgb-to-world transform and then moving it to the depth camera's coordinate system with the world-to-depth transform the correspondence can be created.

Important to note that although the information transfer is resolved the info that I want to transfer is not. It is important to not only know what objects are present in the scene but also which pixels belong to which object due to the fact that the information is transferred via pixel correspondence. Accomplishing this is done by covering the objects with a mask whose color is unique to the object. By using this method each different color will encode the object's class which will enable us to identify the same objects in the point clouds.

To realize the object detection and segmentation that results in a mask with unique colors for each object I have used the Pixellib [19] library. It is a deep learning based image segmenter algorithm. The library provides two types of segmentation: semantic segmentation when the objects are segmented by category and instance segmentation where each instance of an object is segmented separately. Pixellib consists of two major pretrained models: one trained with PyTorch and one with TensorFlow. These pretrained models can segment an image in a fraction of a second which is an important aspect. Apart from its outstanding performance it is also easy to work with and integrating it to projects is a straight-forward task.

4.2.2 Step 2: Plane segmentation

During the object detection phase the resulting masks which cover the objects are not pixel perfect. It could happen that the mask covers a wider area than the object. In these cases due to the error, the background behind the object is colored as well with the object's specific color which could cause problems in later steps, for example during the bounding box definition. To eliminate these wrongly colored points without removing the problematic areas all together - to not change the overall structure of the point cloud - I have considered different scenarios when these errors could be present. In most cases these errors are present on flat surfaces that are either behind or under the objects. The elimination of flat surfaces from point clouds are easily achievable with plane segmentation and one of the most widely used algorithm for this is the RANSAC algorithm.

The RANSAC (Random Sample Consensus) algorithm is an iterative algorithm that samples n number of points from the point cloud and fits a plane onto these points. Then it counts the number of points that are close to the plane defined by the n points and if the number of points is greater than a threshold value the plane is accepted and the points that are close to the plane are considered as inliers. The planes segmented during the process are temporarily removed from the point cloud. This process is repeated until the number of iterations reaches a predefined value or no planes are found with enough inliers. The eliminated planes are stored to be able to reconstruct the point cloud once the critical steps that require the segmentations are done. Important to mention that the RANSAC algorithm is sensitive to the inlier threshold value. If the value is high segments that are not planes could also falsely detected and eliminated. On the other hand if the value is too low the algorithm will not be able to remove the plane in its entirety.

4.2.3 Step 3: Point cloud segmentation

Once the pixels that are transferred to incorrect points in the point cloud are excluded the next step is to segment the point cloud into different objects to process them individually. Thanks to the introduction of unique colors for each object this can be executed by simply iterating through the points in the point cloud and grouping the points based on their color. However, in many cases these point cloud segments - now objects - are not perfect. They could still contain incorrect points and noise. To eliminate these points I have used the radius outlier removal filter.

The essence of the radius outlier removal filter is to remove points that do not have enough neighbours in an r radius sphere around them. It was important to consider that the object point clouds have various sizes and densities, thus the value of r had to be dynamically calculated for each object based on the number of points in the object point cloud.

4.2.4 Step 4: Bounding box definition

Now that the objects are segmented and filtered the bounding boxes can be defined for each object. A bounding box is a three-dimensional set of 8 points that contains a predefined set of points. There are different ways to define such bounding boxes and in my case I had to consider the category the object was in. As I wrote in the introduction of this section in the second method the objects were separated into two categories: bodies of revolution and every other object. The reasoning behind this approach is down to the

Figure 4.2: Rotation along the different axes [20]

way objects are captured by the depth sensing camera.

Also, the definition of the bounding boxes was simplified due to prior knowledge. The objects in consideration are situated on a flat surface (table, floor, etc.) which reduces the degrees of freedom by two. The roll and the pitch (rotation around the x and y axis) of the object is 0. Only the yaw (rotation around the z axis) can be variable. A visual representation of the rotations along the axes can be seen in Figure 4.2.

Reference vertex: It is important to mention that although the bounding box definition is an important step, but to replace the objects also the reference point has to be considered. This point will be the reference to where to put the model which replaces the object. The selected reference vertex in both cases is the vertex that is closest to the camera and the lowest in the world coordinate frame. Lowest because the objects are situated on a flat surface and closest because usually the missing part is roughly along the line between the object and the camera.

Bodies of revolution

In most cases the 'face' of an object - the part which is visible from the camera's perspective - is captured with relative accuracy, however the 'back' of the object is not. It is known where the device was at the time of capturing, thus the missing areas are known to be located behind the 'face' of the object, roughly along the line that is drawn

from the device's position to the 'face' of the object. This further reduced the degrees of freedom by one, since the yaw of the object did not contain useful information. Figure 4.3 shows a visual representation of the location of the missing parts. As it can be seen during the projection of the spheres onto the image plane the spheres' 'back' is lost due to the perspective projection, but the missing parts have to be located behind the 'face' of the object as the front parts occlude the back parts. Interpreting the problem this way is highly effective and reduces the calculation by a large margin. We know that it does not matter what angle the object was captured from due to their shape, thus the unseeable part will be the same in all cases.

Taking this into consideration the bounding box definition for bodies of revolution is very simple. I only have to find the minimal and maximal points along each axis in the world coordinate frame with a simple min or max search.

Arbitrary objects

Since in case of regular objects the unseeable part of the object is not the same from every angle the bounding box definition is more complex. Also, it has to be considered that for example a TV screen or a laptop, the object can be captured badly. This means the edges of the objects will not correct thus only a min or max search as previously would not work in all cases. The solution to this problem is to find the minimal volume bounding box.

In these cases the yaw could not be disregarded since it could contain variable information about the orientation of the object. The impact of projecting arbitrary objects from different views can be seen on Figure 4.5. It is important to notice that the projection can

Figure 4.3: Location of missing parts in case of bodies of revolution [21]

Figure 4.4: Minimal bounding box definition [22]

Figure 4.5: Impact of projecting arbitrary objects from different views [23]

highly differ from different views. Considering this, the bounding boxes' orientation had to be considered. Acquiring bounding boxes that are minimal in volume was achieved through iteration. In each iteration a bounding box was defined using the axis in the world coordinate frame, and its volume was measured. Then the object point cloud was rotated by a predefined angle and the bounding box definition and volume measurement was recalculated. This process was repeated until the measurements were calculated in all the angles in the predefined range. Then the bounding box with the minimal volume was selected as the final bounding box. This method proved to be fast and robust for arbitrary objects. The first and last iteration of this process can be seen on Figure 4.4.

4.2.5 Step 5: Object replacement

Now that the objects are segmented, filtered and the bounding boxes are defined the next step is to replace the objects. The most important aspect of a good object re-

placement was to correctly define the bounding box of an object point cloud. It was also important to define the bounding boxes of the models that are being placed into the scene. For each model the same bounding box definition process was applied as for the objects. As this was done the model's position now is defined by the bounding box more specifically by its reference vertex. If this process was executed correctly finding the place where the model should be placed is down to matching the reference vertices of the object's bounding box and the model's bounding box.

Scaling

The models that are being loaded into the scene come from a database where each object has a default orientation and size. Orientation was important to be uniform so that later on in case of models that had to be rotated to fit perfectly into the scene the rotation can be given with regard to the default orientation. The scaling however had to be applied in both cases. An object's size while in real life is constant, capturing it with a camera can result in different sizes depending on the distance from the camera. The farther the object is from the camera the smaller it will be on the image and thus the smaller it will be in the point cloud. Thus finding the correct scaling factor was important to create a realistic scene. As with the positioning of the models during replacing the scaling was also highly dependent on the bounding box definition. If the bounding boxes are defined correctly the height of the bounding box can be used to find the scaling factor. By calculating the distance between the minimal and maximal value along the z axis of the objects bounding box and the model's bounding box the scaling factor can be calculated by dividing the two values. Then scaling the model's point cloud with the resulting scaling factor will result in a model that has the same height as the object.

Bodies of revolution

In case of bodies of revolution the orientation of the object in the scene has no impact in the replacement process, as in this case the view of this object is the same from every angle. Thus, it was down to transform the model's bounding box to the object's bounding box with respect to the reference vertices.

Arbitrary objects

In case of arbitrary objects the orientation of the object in the scene has a huge impact in the replacement process (Figure 4.5), which first has to be determined so the model

point cloud could be rotated to the correct orientation and then the reference vertices could be matched.

Orientation estimation

To overcome the problem presented by the unknown orientation multiple methods were considered, but the most promising one was to use the RGB image to estimate the orientation of the object. The idea here was that given an RGB image from where the object is cropped out the yaw - rotation along the z axis - of the object could be estimated. For this the most promising method was to use a convolutional neural network that classifies the image based on the yaw of the object. The estimation could have been done with regression, which is more conventional for such problems where the exact output group - class - is not known and rather a numeric value is expected in a predefined range. However, considering that the RGB images are quite low resolution and the motion blur in some cases were significant I have decided to use classification to try to limit the effect of these problems by giving an easier task to the network. Of course to be able to solve this classification I had to have a dataset that contains RGB images of the objects from various angles and the corresponding yaw values to be able to create the training pairs.

Dataset: To create the dataset and to have perfect angle values I have used synthetic data provided by ShapeNet. ShapeNet is a large and diverse dataset of 3D CAD (Computer Aided Design) models that contains 3D models of various objects from different categories. Thanks to the very well organized CAD models I was able to select multiple models for each category to create a dataset that could yield a robust prediction model.

Now that the CAD models are acquired I had to create RGB image - angle pairs. For this I have used a rendering engine called Blender. Blender is a free and open source 3D creation suite that is capable of rendering 3D models into 2D images. Although Blender is a very powerful tool with many options and settings, I only needed the basic functionality to render the images. Thus, I have utilized a renderer [24] that uses Blender's API to render objects from the ShapeNet dataset into RGB images. By specifying the angles from where I want the objects to be rendered I was able to create the dataset.

Important to mention that for every object a separate dataset was created. This meant that for every object a separate neural network had to be trained. This way the results could be more accurate but using each model when needed consumes a lot of memory and processing power. Specific details about the dataset will be discussed in Section 5 and in Table 5.4.

Neural Network: The backbone of this classification is the well known ResNet-50 [25] convolutional neural network. ResNet-50 is a 50 layer deep convolutional neural network that is widely used in computer vision tasks. The input during training was an image with size 512×512 , rendered from a CAD model and the corresponding angle value. The output was a one hot encoded vector that contained the angle class. I have applied the angle error as the loss function, so the task of the neural network was to reduce this error value to a minimum.

Overcoming the problem of the unknown orientation enabled me to handle arbitrary objects as well. To be able to replace these objects I had to crop out the object from the RGB image and using this image to predict the yaw of the object. Once the yaw is known the model point cloud can be rotated to the correct orientation and then the reference vertices can be matched. But before that a uniform starting orientation had to be given to the model point clouds to be able to rotate them to the correct orientation. After this was done the model point cloud can be placed into the scene with the reference vertices matching.

Chapter 5

Results

Presentation of the results and complications of each approach's steps will follow a similar manner and structure as in Chapter 4. I will present the subresults and the final results of the approaches. The results and methods are primarily tested and evaluated on indoor data as the main aim of this work was to outline the possibilities of environment completion in indoor settings, where complex or smaller objects are more common. For the sake of completeness some tests were also performed on outdoor data to see how would the performance change.

5.1. Evaluation of the Deep Learning based approach

5.1.1 Evaluation of the dataset

Data capturing

As I have written in the in Section 4.1.1 a dataset had to be created to be able to perform the training of the neural network. I created this dataset by capturing depth images of multiple different objects with the HoloLens 2 device, from many different angles and distances. My dataset consisted of 18 different objects with various number of depth images per object. Table 5.1 shows the number of depth images per object in the dataset. As it can be seen on Table 5.1 the number of depth images per object varies between 55 and 308. This is down to the inconsistency of the depth image capturing process of the HoloLens 2 device. As I have mentioned in Section 3.3 the depth sensing camera is able to capture between 1 - 5 fps in Long Throw mode. However, my experience with the device was that the frame rate is rarely higher than 4 fps and it is usually around 1 - 2 fps. Important to note that during capture the device was not running any other

application, only the depth sensing and the RGB camera was active. The dataset was captured over a period of 1 week, the low fps values are not a consequence of overuse of the device. Around 3 to 4 objects were captured per session and the device temperature was notably higher towards the end of a capturing session while the processing power was noticeably lower resulting in lower frames per second. The decreasing performance effected the correct capturing of the orientation of the device for each depth image, introducing noise in later steps.

It is also important to highlight that since the dataset was captured during a period of 1 week the lighting conditions were not the same during the whole process. This could have been avoided by capturing the dataset in a controlled environment with constant lighting conditions in an empty room, however such an environment was not available.

Object	Depth images [pcs]	Capture duration [s]	fps [$\frac{1}{s}$]
watering can	254	90.21	2.82
plant	299	98.04	3.05
ping pong racket	203	64.00	3.17
chair	74	73.07	1.01
camera tripod	63	62.01	1.01
umbrella	59	58.02	1.01
cleaner bottle 1	308	79.80	3.86
cleaner bottle 2	226	63.20	3.58
cleaner bottle 3	68	67.02	1.01
bag	55	54.02	1.02
bowl	77	76.03	1.01
laptop	73	72.03	1.01
teddy bear	214	63.80	3.35
joystick	243	64.40	3.77
camera lens	243	67.60	3.59
garbage shovel	184	57.00	3.23
wheelbarrow	284	80.40	3.53
Total	2927	1190,65	-
Average	172,17	70.04	2.46

Table 5.1: Number of depth images per object in the dataset

Apart from the circumstances an acceptable environment could be used where the objects were placed on a table and the device was moved around the table in a circular motion, capturing the objects from all angles and distances. Although the object selection was limited my aim was to capture objects that have numerous aspects that would be captured wrongly in case of a single depth image, focusing on narrow, thin and shiny objects.

Conclusion of data capture: Considering the circumstances the dataset quality is suitable to verify that a neural network based approach can work or not. More captures would have been better, however it has to be noted that capturing and post-processing a single object took a lot of time as the parameters of different post-processing steps had to be adjusted manually for each object. The device has also frozen on several occasions further slowing down the process. Also, the usage time of the device was limited by the battery life, which was around 2 hours.

Data post-processing

The data post-processing consisted of 4 steps:

1. Creating a high definition point cloud from the depth images
2. Point cloud filtering of the merged point cloud
3. Generating the GT images: projecting the merged and filtered point cloud from multiple angles
4. Generating the mask images: finding the difference between a raw and the GT images

Creating a high definition point cloud from the depth images: The depth images were captured from many different angles and distances relative to the objects, thus to acquire a high definition point cloud the partial point clouds projected from the depth images had to be merged together. For this the first step was to project the depth images from two-dimensions to three-dimensions. This was calculated with the look-up table provided by the HoloLens 2 device and the depth values. Multiplying the pixel's depth value with the corresponding value from the look-up table as shown in Equation 5.1 resulted in a three-dimensional point cloud. In Equation 5.1 $[x, y, z]$ is the three-dimensional point, *table* is the look-up table provided by the device, *depth* is the depth

image and u and v are the pixel coordinates in the depth image. The elements of the lookup table are three-dimensional vectors, thus the result of the multiplication is also a three-dimensional vector, which's end point is the three-dimensional point.

$$\forall u \in [1, 288], \forall v \in [1, 320] : [x, y, z] = table[u, v] \cdot depth[u, v] \quad (5.1)$$

The result of projecting a single depth image to three-dimensions can be observed on Figure 5.1. As it can be seen the point cloud is missing a lot of details. The most significant lost depth values are encountered at thin and narrow parts of the wheelbarrow. The upper part of the object is missed completely as Figure 5.1 c and d shows. The depth camera also misses the unseen part of the object from the given perspective. The outline of the wheelbarrow on the wall behind it on Figure 5.1 c is caused by the depth camera being obscured by the object.

(a) Depth image

(b) Reference RGB image

(c) Point cloud of the depth image -
front view

(d) Point cloud of the depth image -
side view

Figure 5.1: Point cloud of a depth image

The result of applying Equation 5.1 to all the depth images of an object and merging them can be seen on Figure 5.2. Noticeably the resulting point cloud contain much more points and the object is more detailed, especially the thin and narrow parts. The unseen

(a) Merged raw point cloud of multiple depth images - front view (b) Merged raw point cloud of multiple depth images - side view

Figure 5.2: Merged point cloud of multiple depth images

parts of the object are also recovered. However, the point cloud contains a lot of noise, which is caused by the invalid measurements of the depth camera.

Point cloud filtering: The point clouds generated in the previous step contained a lot of noise, thus a filtering step was needed to remove the noise. Statistical outlier filter was applied to the point clouds to remove the noise to only keep parts of the point cloud that is part of the object. The algorithm can be characterized with 2 parameters: the number of neighbours to consider and the standard deviation multiplier. The more neighbours are and less the standard deviation multiplier is the more points will be removed from the point cloud. In my case an aggressive filtering was needed to remove the noise. The specific parameters used for each object was different due to the different number of points in the point clouds and the different level of the noise. The result of the filtering can be seen on Figure 5.3. With the right parameters the filtering was able to remove the noise resulting in a very well detailed object point cloud.

Generating the GT images: To generate the GT images first the now filtered and detailed object point clouds had to be projected back to 2 dimensions with regard to the camera pose. This was done using the pinhole camera model. The image planes to project the merged and filtered point cloud were the same as the ones that were used during the creation of the single depth images. Thus, I will have the original faulty depth images and the projected point clouds from the same angle. The result of projecting the detailed point cloud can be seen on Figure 5.4. It is clear that a lot of features and details could be recovered thanks to process of merging and filtering multiple point clouds.

The images that were used during the world coordinate based approach were generated similarly. The only difference was that each point cloud points' world coordinate was saved to the pixel where the point would project to not the distance value from the camera.

Figure 5.3: Merged and filtered point cloud of multiple depth images

Figure 5.4: Original and GT depth image

Figure 5.5: Original and GT depth image

Generating the mask images: The mask images were generated by finding the difference between the original depth image and the merged point cloud projected from the same angle. The resulting images can be seen on Figure 5.5. The masks are correctly covering the areas where the capturing of the objects failed. However, in some cases areas not part of the objects are also covered by the mask, which is not ideal but acceptable.

Conclusion of data post-processing: The goals to have GT and mask images for each object was achieved successfully. The GT images are detailed and the masks are covering the areas where the capturing of the objects failed, with some occasional noise in the masks.

5.1.2 Evaluation of the neural networks

Two different data representations were considered for the neural network: images with depth information and images with coordinate information. The input for the neural network were not single images with the corresponding masks but multiple images of the same object from different angles and distances which were randomly selected. Considering this a sample of input data (input image, GT image, mask) can be seen on Figure 5.6 in case of the depth information based method which will be shown later. It was extremely important to match the correct images to the correct masks to be able to avoid unwanted results. This required some prethinking and planning before the training process, but was manageable.

(a) Input depth images

(b) Input GT images

(c) Input masks

Figure 5.6: Input data sample

Training process: In both cases the training process was similar, only the input data was different. In each forward pass the neural network was fed with a batch of input data. The batch size was 8, meaning that 8 image sequences were fed to the network in each forward pass. First the input images were fed to the generator network which generated the inpainted images and then the inpainted images were fed to the discriminator network which predicted whether the images were real or fake. Once the discriminator network finished its forward pass the loss was calculated for both the generator and the discriminator network and the weights were updated during the backpropagation process.

Depth information based neural network

Two-dimensional results: The result of the training process was evaluated using two different viewpoints. Firstly the results were examined in two-dimension by comparing the input and the output images. This aspect was important to see the completion

was completed at the desired pixels and whether the results were interpretable in two-dimensions. The result of the depth image completion can be seen on Figure 5.7 where the first row represents the input images, the second row the predictions and the third row the GT images. Comparing the input to the predictions the improvement is clear. Areas where the completion was performed had been filled with depth values that are expected for the object.

Figure 5.7: Results of the depth information based completion in two-dimensions. From top to bottom: input images, predictions, GT images

Numerical evaluation: To numerically evaluate the difference between the ground truth and the predicted images two metrics were used: the mean absolute error (MAE) 5.2 and the mean squared error (RMSE) 5.3. The difference between the GT and the predicted images were only calculated in the masked areas as everywhere else the two images are the same. Calculating the errors for the whole images would have resulted in a much lower error due to the many pixels that are the same in the GT and the predicted images. The errors can be seen in Table 5.2 and it represents the error for all the test images. The errors are relatively low, however it has to be noted that in indoor environments even a small error can be significant.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (5.2)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (5.3)$$

MAE[m]:	0.2959
RMSE[m]:	0.0128

Table 5.2: MAE and RMSE errors of the depth information based completion in meters

Three-dimensional results: The second aspect of the evaluation was to examine the results in three-dimensions. The two-dimension to three-dimension conversion was performed by the same process as before but with the output images. The evaluation in three-dimensions is important to verify that the neural network was able to learn the structural information at the missing object areas. The result of the completion in three-dimension can be seen on Figure 5.8. As the results show the neural network was not able to fully learn the structural information at the missing object areas. Although it is not correct, the results are not completely wrong or random. Firstly it is important to note that the neural network trained enough to not predict unlikely depth values, meaning the range in which the missing values were expected was learned. The main error and uncertainty comes when the exact depth value is to be predicted within that correctly learnt range. It is also notable that not all the predicted values are wrong. Although there is noise in the prediction, the correct points are in majority. This can be especially seen on a 5.8 a where the outline of the garbage shovel is clearly denser than the noisy areas.

In order to overcome the noise, parameter tuning was performed, however the results did not improve. Since the neural network itself was able to learn the correct range of depth values and start to move the points to the right direction led me to the conclusion that the problem is probably with the amount and the variety of the data. For a network with as many parameters as GAN has, the train data was not sufficient to learn the structural information of the objects perfectly, only an initial understanding was achieved. This is also supported by the fact that the results were better for objects with more depth images in the dataset.

Figure 5.8: Results of the depth information based completion in three-dimensions

World coordinate based neural network

Results of the world coordinate based approach was evaluated by heavily relying on the reasoning that the provided data was not enough to train the neural network. The lack of sufficient quantity of data will cumulatively worsen the result of this approach. To see why the following reasoning can be considered: In case of the depth information based approach the variable that had to be predicted was the only depth value of a pixel. Meaning that the neural network had to predict n number of values which is equal to the number of pixels to be inpainted. Considering that in this approach for a single pixel three values were assigned (x, y, z) the number of values to be predicted was $3n$. Meaning that at the least it had to learn 3 times more information than the depth information based approach.

Numerical evaluation: The numeric evaluation of the world coordinate based approach was performed similarly to the depth information based approach, but paying attention to the different data representation. The errors can be seen in Table 5.3 and it represents the error for all the test images. Comparing the errors to the depth information based approach it is clear that the errors are higher in this case, as it was predicted. Notable that the RMSE is lower in case of the world coordinate based approach, which is due to many outliers in the predicted values. The results of the world coordinate based

MAE[m]:	0.8291
RMSE[m]:	0.0034

Table 5.3: MAE and RMSE errors of the depth information based completion in meters

approach can be seen on Figure 5.9. As it was expected the results were worse than the depth information based approach. The network was not able to learn any structural information of the objects. On Figure 5.9 a and b the garbage shovel was merged into the background wall while on Figure 5.9 c and d it disappeared completely.

(a) Completion result of garbage shovel in 3D

(b) Completion result of garbage shovel in 3D

(c) Completion result of wheelbarrow in 3D - side view

(d) Completion result of wheelbarrow in 3D - front view

Figure 5.9: Results of the world coordination based completion in three-dimensions

5.2. Evaluation of the direct approach

The direct approach was considered as a consequence of the problem emerged during the evaluation of the Deep Learning based approach. Before I would start generating a larger and more diverse dataset I wanted to see if the direct approach could be a better and faster solution. The huge advantage of the direct approach compared to the Deep Learning based approach is that it does not require a dataset to be trained on, thereby bypassing the problems of the first approach.

As I have mentioned in Section 4.2 to be able to achieve good results all the steps of this approach had to be as robust as possible due to the multiple interdependent steps. It could be easily seen that a small amount of noise in the starting steps could snowball into a huge error in the final result.

As this approach was considered as a possible workaround for the problems of the Deep Learning based approach it was not tested and evaluated for any possible object, it was tested as a proof of concept. I have tested the algorithm on a few highly different objects. If this solution was able to perform robustly on these objects it would be a good sign that it could be used for other objects as well.

The main steps of the direct method can be examined on Figure 5.10. The steps will be evaluated in the same order as they are presented on the figure.

It is also important to mention that numerical evaluation in case of the direct approach is not possible in a way to be comparable to the deep learning based approach. This is due to the difference in dimensionality of the data. In this case the processes performed in three-dimensions while in the deep learning based approach the processes were performed in two-dimensions.

5.2.1 Evaluation of step 1: Object detection and segmentation

Firstly the object detection and segmentation had to be resolved. As I have written in Section 4.2 the RGB images were utilized for this task and the information was transferred to the depth image via pixel correspondence. For this a method had to be used that enabled me to mark the pixels that belong to a specific object. Fortunately the Pixellib library provides - among many other - a tool for this task. The result of the object detection and segmentation was the original image, but with a transparent differently colored mask over each object which was considered. This result (Figure 5.11 b) was not yet able to be used for the next step, it had to be modified. Firstly since the masks'

transparency could result in wrong object segmentation in later steps as the specific colors were used throughout the whole process. This was achieved by using the output of the object detection and segmentation differently. Since the result of this process was a dictionary where the key values were the detected objects and the values were the pixel coordinates of that object. Using this dictionary I was able to create a new image where I would manually paint over each pixel with an object specific color resulting in a non-transparent mask. Important to note that I have created a dictionary in which the keys were the object names that were considered and the values were the different color values for each object. This made it possible to identify each object later by their color only. Secondly for both visual and robustness reasons any color information had to be removed from the image which were not related to the object segmentation. Performing this had to be thought through as from one hand I wanted to have colors on specific areas but on the other hand I wanted a grayscale image everywhere else. The solution was to transform the image into a 3 channel grayscale image, meaning for each pixel the RGB values were the same, which enabled to use colors on specific pixels. The result of these changes performed on Figure 5.11 c can be seen on Figure 5.11 d.

Figure 5.10: Steps of the direct method

Figure 5.11: Steps of the object detection and segmentation

The results on the RGB camera's frame was satisfying, but now the gathered information had to be transferred to the depth image. For each camera on the HoloLens 2 device the transformation from one camera's frame to another can be calculated by involving the world coordinate system. The world coordinate system is uniform for all the cameras on the device - as it was mentioned in Section 3.3 - thus by first transforming the pixel coordinates from the RGB camera space to the world coordinate system and then from the world coordinate system to the depth image the pixel correspondence can be achieved and the results can be visualized in three-dimensions as the depth image can be projected to a point cloud. The result of the segmentation in three-dimensions can be seen on Figure 5.12 a and b. As it can be seen the segmentation using the RGB camera's images could be transferred correctly and useably to three-dimensions. Examining the errors along the edges of the objects can be observed. As the segmentation mask were not pixel perfect in some cases areas near the objects edges were also considered part of the object. These errors were then transferred to the depth images and then to three-dimensions, where the badly segmented areas were projected to the wall or to the floor - depending on the point of view. A zoomed in example of this error can be seen on Figure 5.12 c.

(a) Segmented scene in three-dimensions - view 1

(b) Segmented scene in three-dimensions - view 1

(c) Wrongly projected points

Figure 5.12: Results of the object detection and segmentation in three-dimensions

5.2.2 Evaluation of step 2: Plane segmentation

To precede any future errors originating from the previous step I performed the plane segmentation. The RANSAC algorithm was utilized to remove the significant planes from the point cloud and the processes result can be seen on Figure 5.13. The red colored points were removed from the point cloud.

(a) 1st iteration of RANSAC

(b) 2nd iteration of RANSAC

Figure 5.13: Results of RANSAC plane segmentation

5.2.3 Evaluation of step 3: Point cloud segmentation

After the falsely colored points in the point cloud were removed the next step was to separate the individual objects from the point cloud and start the object replacement. Thanks to the previous steps this process was easily manageable by simply relying on the RGB values which were specifically assigned to each object. Thus, the isolation of the objects was a matter of grouping the points with the same RGB values together into a dictionary and adding the object's name to the corresponding points as the key value. The result of this process can be seen on Figure 5.14. As the Figure shows there were still some unwanted points (marked with red color) separated along with the objects which had to be dealt with. Due to these few points being well separated from the actual object points the solution was to apply a radius outlier filter which removes points that are too far from the dense areas of the point cloud. The result of the radius outlier filter can be seen on Figure 5.14 marked with red. By applying this filter the remaining points could be further processed in the following steps.

Figure 5.14: Results of separating the plant object from the point cloud

5.2.4 Evaluation of step 4: Bounding box definition

All the preceding step's goal was to convert the input data into well separated and noise free object specific point clouds so that the bounding box definition could be performed such that the inlier points in the bounding box would be only the points of an object. This is the step where the relevance of the two categories of bodies of revolution and arbitrary objects comes into play. As many evaluation and testing performed during this research it became clear that the bounding box definition has to be different for these two categories. The reasoning behind this is that in case of simpler objects like bodies of revolution the bounding box definition can be much faster and less robust due to not having to consider the orientation of the object. Less robust in this sense means that fewer

steps had to be performed to be able to define the bounding boxes. In case of arbitrary objects some additional steps had to be implemented to ensure that the replacement was performed correctly.

The reference vertex definition in both cases was the same. First the lower set of points had to be determined which was sorting the points by their z coordinate and then from these 4 points find the one that is closest to the camera's position at the time of capturing. This was manageable by calculating all four points and the camera's distance in the three-dimensional space and selecting the one with the lowest value.

Bodies of revolution

In case of bodies of revolution the bounding box definition was performed by finding the minimum and maximum values along the x , y and z axis in the world coordinate space. No further action had to be taken as - mentioned in Section 4.2 - the object in question was located on a surface parallel to the floor. The resulting point cloud in case of a body of revolution can be seen on Figure 5.15.

(a) Bounding box of the vase - front view (b) Bounding box of the vase - top view

(c) Bounding box of the vase and the plant - full scene

Figure 5.15: Results of the object detection and segmentation in three-dimensions

Arbitrary objects

In case of arbitrary objects the bounding box was not as straight forward as in case of bodies of revolution. Here the orientation of an object could not be disregarded because it stores a lot of information about what way the object is facing. This complication was solved in multiple steps from which the first was to define the bounding boxes so that their volume would be minimal indicating additional information of the object's shape. To acquire such bounding boxes some factors had to be considered, from which the most important was that not a globally minimal bounding box had to be found. The fact that the objects are on a flat surface here also applies and is a useful information that should not be disregarded. Thus, the objective was to find a minimal bounding box by only allowing the bounding box to be rotated around the z axis - which is perpendicular to the floor. This was done by rotating the object point cloud around the z axis in small steps and calculating the volume of the bounding box for each rotation using the same method as in case of bodies of revolution. After all the possible angles were evaluated the minimal volume was selected and the corresponding bounding box was used for the next step.

5.2.5 Evaluation of step 5: Object replacement

As with the bounding box definition, the object replacement was also different for bodies of revolution and arbitrary objects. From some aspect the two processes were similar, but for the arbitrary objects once again required some additional steps to be performed. Also important to mention that to replace the objects with the corresponding models the bounding box of the models had to be also created. The model's bounding box definition was performed in the same way as in case of the objects, so for bodies of revolution using the minimum and maximum values along the x , y and z axis and for arbitrary objects using the minimal volume bounding box along the z axis.

Scale

Firstly the scaling had to be addressed. The scaling factor was calculated by dividing the size along the z axis of the objects bounding box with the size along the z axis of the models bounding box - as described in Section 4.2. The first major limitation of the direct approach was encountered here. In some cases when the object was captured so that the missing parts were on the top or the bottom of the object the scaling factor was not correctly defined. Missing the bottom part would have been acceptable as the object

would have been placed on a flat surface. This surface was big enough to not be missed in any case during capturing thus using the plane's equation that is right under an object would have been a good approximation, but the missing values at the top could not be substituted similarly. Fortunately this error was experienced only in a limited number of cases.

Bodies of revolution

As described in Section 4.2 the replacement of bodies of revolution was performed by simply finding the bounding box and the reference vertex of the model than scaling the model to the correct size and then matching the reference vertices of the model and the object. The resulting replacement generated for bodies of revolution was very promising and can be seen on the second row of Figure 5.16. The result improved the original point cloud in terms of details, reduced noise and multi-view consistency.

Figure 5.16: Result of object replacement for bodies of revolution

Arbitrary objects

As written in Section 4.2 for the replacement of arbitrary objects the orientation had to be defined for which the RGB images were used.

Orientation estimation: The RGB image based orientation estimation was carried out using a neural network. The network's task would be that given an object as an RGB image the network would have to predict the orientation of the object. To accomplish this first an appropriate dataset had to be generated. The dataset consisted of image - angle pairs. To be able to have precise angles synthetic data was used to produce the dataset. For this the specific categories from the ShapeNet dataset were used. Initially to try out the method only a few categories included in Table 5.4 were used. For the different objects different number of CAD models were available in the ShapeNet database thus the number of different models for each category varied. Although the number of models were different for each category the number of images generated for each model was the same. Creating the dataset from these three-dimensional CAD models was performed using rendering. This enabled me to precisely define from what positions I want to create a snapshot of the object which was crucial for a good dataset. The camera positions during rendering were all positioned on a sphere around the object. The CAD models were rendered from 72 different angles and 4 different height levels along z axes. The angles were defined as every 5th angle in the range of 0 to 360 degrees and the height levels were defined as 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 times the height of the object. This way for a single CAD model 288 renderings were done from different positions covering all the possible angles from where the object would get captured by the HoloLens 2 device. The specific camera position during rendering of the dataset can be seen on Figure 5.17 and sample images from the dataset can be seen on Figure 5.18 showcasing the different height levels with a constant angle. It can also be seen on the example images that the renderings are blurry. This was performed to simulate the noise and low resolution of the RGB camera of the HoloLens 2 device.

Network architecture: As mentioned in Section 4.2 the network architecture was the ResNet50 network which I used with pretrained weights at the beginning. The network was trained for 20 epochs with a batch size of 164. The learning rate was set to 0.001 and the patience was set to 5. The loss function was the absolute mean error (MAE) between the predicted and the ground truth angles. The training was performed on a

Name	Number of 3D CAD models	Number of renderings
keyboard	65	18720
laptop	100	28800
monitor	72	20736
car	77	22176

Table 5.4: Dataset for RGB image based orientation estimation

Figure 5.17: Camera position during rendering

Figure 5.18: Result of object replacement for bodies of revolution

single NVIDIA 12 GB GeForce GTX 1080 Ti GPU and took approximately 5 hours, depending on the number of epochs and input data.

The results on the testing images were accurate, missing the correct orientation with only one step.

Object replacement: Now that I had a working solution to estimate the objects' orientation the replacement could be performed on arbitrary objects. Essentially the steps to be performed were the same as in case of bodies of revolution, but with the additional step of cropping the object from the RGB image, feeding it to the neural network to predict its orientation and then rotating the model with the predicted angle. After the rotation was performed the scaling factor and the reference vertex of the model point cloud could be defined. By matching the reference vertices of the model and the object replacement was finished. Results of replacing arbitrary objects can be seen on Figure 5.19. On Figure 5.19 a and b the scene's RGB and depth images can be seen. By analyzing the depth image it can be seen that the objects were captured with relatively good quality. However, visualizing the point cloud of the scene (Figure 5.19 c and d) it can be seen that the point cloud is noisy and the objects especially the keyboard is hardly recognizable. On images e and f the result of the object replacement can be seen. The replacement was performed correctly with minor errors regarding the scaling and the exact orientation.

The errors regarding the orientation estimation could be explained by the following factors:

1. The RGB camera's performance of the HoloLens 2 device is highly dependent on the lighting conditions. If lighting conditions were good the shutter speed - the time needed to capture an image - was low and movement during capturing did not affect the data. However, if the data was collected in a room where only artificial light was available the shutter speed was high which introduced motion blur resulting in a blurry image. The object detection and segmentation was not highly effected by the minor motion blur but for the orientation estimation it was a problem.
2. Apart from the occasional motion blur the RGB camera's resolution and sharpness was also a problem. The resolution limitation was addressed by blurring the images during dataset generation, however the sharpness could not be solved this way.
3. The dataset was mostly created using objects with no color information. This was mainly due to the fact that not every ShapeNet CAD model had color information,

Figure 5.19: Result of object replacement for arbitrary objects

most of them was just a three-dimensional mesh model. This also could confuse the neural network as on real data, color is a common feature regardless of the object.

5.3. Results on outdoor data

The main aim of this research was to be able to perform environment completion in indoor settings. The indoor areas were in the focus because the most common issues with data capturing are present indoor. Smaller and more complex objects are more

common in such areas, thus the biggest upgrade in terms of environment completion could be achieved here. However, for the sake of completeness I have also tested mainly the direct approach on outdoor data. In outdoor environments the main issue are the harsh lighting conditions. As described earlier in Chapter 3 the device's depth sensing camera is sensitive to infrared light, thus the sunlight can cause problems. This issue is further enhanced by the fact that outdoor environments usually contain more objects that are reflective or transparent. To list a few examples of these objects: windows, water, cars, etc. Another problem is that the outdoor objects are usually much bigger than indoor objects and this combined with the previously described problems could enhance the error during the scaling step.

Deep Learning based approach: In case of the Deep Learning based approach the issue which arised during the evaluation of outdoor data was the lack of training data. This error would be further enhanced due the lack of outdoor objects in the dataset, thus retraining the network with more indoor and outdoor objects would be necessary. Considering the combination of these two factors the network was not tested on outdoor data as it was clear that the results would not result in a meaningful feedback.

Direct approach: In case of the direct approach the car object was selected as the main testing object. The reason behind this was that a car has all the features that would be problematic for the depth sensing camera of the HoloLens 2 device:

- The car is a big object, thus the scaling could be effected
- The car is reflective having both mirrors and transparent parts, thus the depth sensing camera could have problems capturing the depth image
- The car has more complex parts thus the detail enhancement could be tested

In light of these problematic features if the algorithm was able to perform well on a car it would be a good sign that it could perform well on other outdoor objects also. Some other objects were also tested but the car was the main focus. The resulting images can be seen on Figure 5.20 and on Figure 5.21. On Figure 5.20 the replacement of a laptop and a bottle can be seen. In case of the bottle the replacement was performed correctly and a lot of information was added to the scene. The laptop was also correctly detected, but the scale and orientation was not correctly estimated. However, comparing the result of the completion to the input depth image - note the missing laptop - the results are containing more information than the input even if they are not perfect. In case of the

Figure 5.20: Result of object replacement for arbitrary objects in outdoor environment (indoor objects)

car's replacement (Figure 5.21) the orientation was found correctly, but the scale is highly inaccurate. It is caused by one of the problem I mentioned earlier, that the car is a big object. The depth sensing camera was not able to capture the whole car in one frame which effected the scaling. On Figure 5.21 a,c and d the marked areas are the headrest of the car's seats. Since this was the highest point of the car that was captured by the depth sensing camera the scaling was based on this point. This resulted in a much smaller car than it should have been.

(a) RGB image of the scene

(b) Depth image of the scene

(c) Input point cloud - front view

(d) Input point cloud - right view

(e) Output point cloud - front view

(f) Output point cloud - right view

Figure 5.21: Result of object replacement for arbitrary objects in outdoor environment (outdoor object)

5.4. Comparison of the two approaches

There are many aspects to compare the two approaches. Considering the approaches a possible use case is a real time application, thus runtime is an important aspect. However, running such a complex algorithm real time natively on the HoloLens 2 device is not feasible at the moment due to the limited processing power of the device. However, the

improvement of the hardware is a continuous process and in the future it could be possible to run such an algorithm on the device. Apart from the runtime, the quality, robustness and applicability of the approaches are also important. In the following sections I will compare the two approaches based on these aspects.

5.4.1 Runtime

In both cases the runtimes were tested on a single image. The following hardware and operating system were used:

- CPU: Intel® Core™ i7-7700K CPU @ 4.20GHz
- GPU: NVIDIA 12 GB GeForce GTX 1080 Ti
- RAM: 64 GB DDR4
- OS: Ubuntu 22.04

Deep Learning based approach: The runtime of the Deep Learning based approach is highly dependent on the hardware used. In my case the runtime was around 0.2 seconds. This low evaluation time is not surprising as after the correct weights were loaded the evaluation of the network is a simple forward pass. With this runtime a real time application would be feasible given that the hardware is powerful enough.

Direct approach: The runtime of the direct approach depends on various factors. Mainly because the approach consists of multiple steps and the runtime of each step is different and depends on actual data that is being processed. The main bottleneck of the runtime is the object detection and segmentation and the orientation estimation in case of arbitrary objects. RANSAC could also slow down the process due to its iterative nature, however in case of point clouds with a few thousand points it should not be a problem.

Thus, for each step the runtime was measured separately. The results can be seen in Table 5.5.

As the results show, the runtime of the direct approach is much higher than the runtime of Deep Learning based approach. Even though the depth sensing camera works with 5 frames per second the runtime of the direct approach is not feasible for a real time application. Optimizing the code would certainly improve the runtime as it was not focused on during the implementation.

Steps	Time [s]
Loading frame data	0.56
Object detection and segmentation	0.21
Pixel correspondence	0.20
RANSAC plane segmentation	0.0004
Point cloud segmentation and object point cloud filtering	0.31
Bounding box definition	0.13
Object replacement (arbitrary)	0.15
Total	1.56

Table 5.5: Runtime of the different steps in the direct approach

The load time during the depth learning based approach was not significant as in that case only 3 images had to be loaded while in this case numerous different data had to be loaded like the depth image, rgb image, point cloud, models, etc..

Conclusion of runtime: The runtime of the deep learning based approach is much lower than the runtime of direct approach due to the number and size of the data to be loaded in case of the direct method As a result of the load time the runtime of the direct approach is not feasible for a real time application at the moment.

5.4.2 Quality of the results

Deep Learning based approach: As of now the quality of the results of the Deep Learning is too noisy to be used in an application, due to the lack of data. Despite the lack of data the results are still better than the original point clouds in some aspect and the progress of the neural network suggests that with more data the results could be improved significantly.

Direct approach: The quality of the direct approach in terms of object replacement is very good as the models that replace the faulty objects are very detailed and contain no noise. In this approach the quality can be better described as the quality of the steps that are performed. The better the position, orientation and scaling, the better the results will be.

Conclusion of the quality of the results: As of now the quality of the results of the direct approach are better than the deep learning based approach even though it is not always producing the correct results. Important to note that numerical comparison between the results is not easy. In case of the deep learning based approach the exact errors could be calculated by comparing the input and output images, but in case of the direct approach such method is not feasible due to the process being in three dimensions.

5.4.3 Robustness

Deep Learning based approach: At this or any other algorithm that is based on neural networks' robustness is very closely related to the quality of the training data. If the data is diverse and numerous enough the network can produce robust results if used correctly. Again the lack of data is the main problem of the Deep Learning based approach in sense of robustness in this case. Nonetheless, the results produced by the network are not random and usually tends to be in the right direction.

Direct approach: The direct approach has proved to be inconsistent in terms of results. The outcome of the process is varying. Due to the many steps and different kind of objects there will always be some cases where the results are not correct. When every step works correctly the results are very good, but if one of the steps fails the results can be underwhelming.

Conclusion of the quality of the robustness: In conclusion the Deep Learning based approach is more robust than the direct approach even though the results are better in case of the direct approach, because when the direct approach fails it fails completely.

5.4.4 Applicability

Deep Learning based approach: In case of the Deep Learning based approach the applicability is limited by the size of the model and the hardware. Given a hardware that is capable of loading the model into the memory of the graphics card the approach is applicable and could be considered light weight.

Direct approach: In case of the direct approach multiple factors limit the applicability. It is important to load multiple data initially to let the CPU focus on the actual processing.

- The HoloLens 2 device's capture with all the RGB images, depth images, point clouds and camera poses for each frame
- The object detection and segmentation model
- The point cloud models that are used for the replacement
- The orientation estimation models for each object category

Considering all these factors and their memory usage it is clear that the direct approach is harder to use and more resource intensive than the Deep Learning based approach.

Conclusion of the quality of the applicability: In conclusion the Deep Learning based approach is more applicable due to the numerous factors that has to be loaded for the direct approach. The inconsistency of the direct approach also makes it harder to use it in an application.

Chapter 6

Summary

Reflecting on the result of the experiments from a technical point of view is an important part of any research. In the following lines I will summarize my experiences with the HoloLens 2 device, findings during the research and the results of the different methods that I have tried out.

6.1. Problem statement

Capturing the environment with every detail preserved with the HoloLens 2 device can be challenging in some cases due to the limitations of the device. In case of small or complex objects the depth sensing camera is not able to capture correctly leaving noise and holes in the pointcloud. The main purpose of this thesis was to find a possible solution to retrieve the lost information and thus to explore the capabilities of the HoloLens 2 in terms of environment completion. As a part of this investigation possible methods were developed to improve the quality of the captured environment's details. The methods were tested on indoor and outdoor environments as well to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed methods.

6.2. HoloLens 2 device

The summary of this thesis is focusing on the device's data capturing capabilities with the forward facing sensors. Capabilities of the device in terms of hand tracking, gesture recognition and other features that are not directly related to the scope of this thesis are not included in the summary.

I have been working with the Microsoft HoloLens 2 device for more than three years mainly focusing on its sensors. I have gained a considerable amount of experience re-

garding the sensors and more importantly I have encountered the main limitations of the data capturing in terms of the quality and consistency.

The HoloLens 2 is a very promising device with a lot of potential in a variety of fields, but it has room for improvement in terms of the quality of the captured data. The most significant problem that I have encountered during my work is the inconsistency of the captured data. The average frame rates per second of the different sensors are not stable and can change rapidly. The 4 head tracking cameras as stated in the device’s technical report are capturing images at 30 frames per second, but in my experience this is not always the case. Furthermore, the images are not synchronized, thus for example in case of stereo vision the calibration is impossible to perform accurately. The inconsistency was also present in case of the depth sensing camera and the RGB camera. Due to the unsynchronized manner of data collection the pixel correspondence from the RGB image to the depth image would also be impossible to perform. However, this has not turned into a major problem since the depth sensing camera was only collecting data at 1-3 frames per second instead of 1-5. This combined with the 30 frames per second RGB camera the inconsistency could be neglected.

The depth sensing camera’s drawbacks are sensor specific (range, multi-bounce, Sun). Overcoming these errors is a universal problem that can be applied to any other time-of-flight based depth sensing camera. Besides the sensor specific errors the low resolution and low frame rate were also limiting factors which are not sensor specific and are present due to the characteristics of the device. These limitations presented the biggest challenge during the research.

Due to the resolution in many cases the environment completion seemed an impossible task because of the lack of details on the depth image or the pointcloud to rely on.

The RGB camera’s 8 megapixel resolution is more than enough for the purpose of the device, however it performed poorly in low light conditions, resulting in motion blur and noise. Since the RGB image is used for the texture of the pointcloud, the noise and the motion blur is also present in the pointcloud. I have also experienced focusing malfunctions in low light conditions.

6.3. Deep learning based approach

A deep learning based method was the starting point of my research. General adversarial networks (GAN) are state-of-the-art methods capable of generating high quality images. In my case not a whole image had to be generated, only some completion had

to be done, where the depth sensing camera failed. For this a database was created with 17 indoor objects, which resulted in almost 3000 training images. Training the network with this amount of data did not prove to be sufficient, thus the network was not able to perform accurately on depth image completion, but it showed promising. Granted that more data would be available for training the network, the results would certainly improve.

A problem that I faced during evaluation of the network was the mask generation. During the setup of the database the masks could be generated as the difference of the GT merged image and the original image. But in a real life scenario the GT image is not available, thus the mask generation would be a challenge.

The result on the two data types were evaluated on indoor data as the dataset was created for indoor objects. The resulting depth images showed better results than the input images, having areas filled with values that express the distance of the object from the camera. Moving into 3 dimensions the results showed a significant drop in quality and rise in noise but the density of the filled areas were the highest at the desired locations.

6.4. Direct approach

The direct approach was considered as a possible solution to the problem of having a low amount of data to train the network. In this method I tried to approach the problem from a different point of view, where the completion could be performed without relying on having a large amount of training data. To adjust that no neural network was involved directly in the process of environment completion only in case of orientation estimation, I have utilized the RGB camera to acquire additional information. A correspondence was established between the RGB and the depth image, introducing colors into 3 dimensional space. Various steps were performed to correctly isolate each object in the scene and later to replace them with high definition models. In case of arbitrary objects an RGB image based orientation estimation method was developed using synthetic data from the ShapeNet dataset. With the combination of all the steps and different submethods the results were promising, but due to the many steps involved in the process the results were not consistent. The robustness of this approach was sufficient but easily breakable.

Tests were also performed on outdoor environments completing the missing parts of a car. As it was expected the results were not as good as in case of indoor environments, due to the object size.

6.5. Possible applications

In this section I will discuss the possible applications of environment completion mainly in indoor settings and in the field of augmented reality.

One of the most promising application of environment completion is the more precise object detection and tracking. A possible application of the first method where only the depth sensing camera was used is to provide an accurate mapping of a scene in pitch dark conditions. In a scenario where no light is present, orientation is very difficult. Wearing the HoloLens 2 device in such condition the environment could be fully mapped thus enabling the user not only to navigate in the dark but to interact with the different objects of use in the scene as well.

Another scenario where these methods could be used is case of a large warehouse where the inventory is constantly changing. In these cases by virtually mapping the warehouse the inventory could be tracked and the items could be located easily. The third method could be used to provide an accurate change detection. For this it is important that all sensors data can be transformed into the world coordinate system. This means that separate data captures can be compared to each other directly by overlaying the different measurements. By doing so both the RGB and the depth images' could provide significant information about the changes in the scene. The RGB image could be used to detect changes of objects while the depth image could be used to specify the exact location and size of the change.

6.6. Possible improvements

Deep learning based approach: In case of the deep learning based approach the areas of improvements are clear: more data is needed for training the network. Once the data is available improvements to the network can also be performed but the changes that has to be made will only be clear once the network is trained on a larger dataset.

Direct approach: In case of the direct approach improvements can be made mainly in the orientation estimation method as the preceding steps' performance is highly limited by the incoming data. The orientation estimation method can be improved by using more varying data for training the network. As of now only the blurriness of the RGB camera is simulated, but adding other factors such as noise and motion blur to the test data would highly improve the robustness of the network. As Figure 5.18 shows the

training images were mostly grayscale due to color not being added to all the CAD models in the ShapeNet dataset. By selecting CAD models with color information the correct orientation estimation would yield better results. The robustness and accuracy of the orientation estimation method can be improved introducing real world images to the training data.

6.7. Future works

As of now the future of the Microsoft HoloLens is uncertain. The development of the HoloLens 3 device has been started but the release date is still unknown. The topic of depth image inpainting and environment completion is a rapidly developing field of research, thus the results and experiences gained from this thesis can be applied to any other TOF depth sensing camera. In my opinion the best results can be achieved with the deep learning based approach as it is more lightweight and easier to improve than the direct approach. The robustness of the two approaches also favors the deep learning based approach as it is more stable and less prone to large errors.

A more various and numerous database is essential to be able to achieve better results thus the first step in my future work would be to create a larger database with more objects and more variations of the same objects. The database should also contain a limited number of outdoor objects to further improve the robustness of the network.

The question of how to generate the masks for the network is still an open issue that has to be solved. The easiest solution would be to mask every difference between a GT and an original image, because in this case the mask generation would only consist of finding the black areas within the depth image. However, for this an extremely detailed pointcloud model of different indoor environments would be needed that is applicable with the device. Creation of such a database is a very time-consuming and expensive task.

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